

Contents lists available at [ScienceDirect](https://www.sciencedirect.com)

European Journal of Surgical Oncology

journal homepage: www.ejso.com

Artificial intelligence in surgical pathology – Where do we stand, where do we go?

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Artificial intelligence
Cancer diagnostics
Machine learning
Imaging
Digital pathology
Mass spectrometry
Optical imaging
Surgical pathology
Spatial biology

ABSTRACT

Surgical and neuropathologists continuously search for new and disease-specific features, such as independent predictors of tumor prognosis or determinants of tumor entities and sub-entities. This is a task where artificial intelligence (AI)/machine learning (ML) systems could significantly contribute to help with tumor outcome prediction and the search for new diagnostic or treatment stratification biomarkers.

AI systems are increasingly integrated into routine pathology workflows to improve accuracy, reproducibility, productivity and to reveal difficult-to-see features in complicated histological slides, including the quantification of important markers for tumor grading and staging.

In this article, we review the infrastructure needed to facilitate digital and computational pathology. We address the barriers for its full deployment in the clinical setting and describe the use of AI in intraoperative or postoperative settings where frozen or formalin-fixed, paraffin-embedded materials are used.

We also summarize quality assessment issues of slide digitization, new spatial biology approaches, and the determination of specific gene-expression from whole slide images. Finally, we highlight new innovative and future technologies, such as large language models, optical biopsies, and mass spectrometry imaging.

1. Introduction

Traditionally, pathological diagnostics of biopsies and tissue resections involve mounting of thin tissue slices on glass slides and the

evaluation under a microscope. Today, with the introduction of digitization of glass slides, pathology assessment can be done virtually on computerized platforms, denoted as Digital Pathology (DP). Digital slides can be analyzed remotely or even sent electronically for second

Abbreviations: AI, artificial intelligence; AIDSS, AI/DL decision support system; COVID, coronavirus disease 2019; DESI, desorption electrospray ionization; DICOM, Digital Imaging and Communications in Medicine; DL, deep learning; DNA, deoxyribonucleic acid; DP, digital pathology; FDA, Food and Drug Administration; FFPE, formalin fixed paraffin embedded; FISH, fluorescence in situ hybridization; FS, frozen section; GBM, glioblastoma multiforme; GPT-4, General Pre-trained Transformer 4; H&E, hematoxylin and eosin; IF, immunofluorescence; IHC, immunohistochemistry; ML, machine learning; KPI, Key Performance Indicator; LLM, large language model; MALDI, matrix-assisted laser-desorption ionization; MSI, mass spectrometry imaging; NEMA, National Electrical Manufacturers Association; OME, Open Microscopy Environment; QF, quality factor; RNA, ribonucleic acid; SRH, Stimulated Raman Histology; TOF, time of flight; ViT, vision transformer; WHO, World Health Organization; WSI, whole slide image.

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<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejso.2024.109541>

Received 30 May 2024; Received in revised form 14 November 2024; Accepted 10 December 2024

Available online 11 December 2024

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opinion. Samuelli et al. describe a multi-center transition experience from glass slides to DP [1].

During the process of digitization, a conventional glass slide is scanned and transformed into a multi-layered, complex digital image, called *Whole Slide Image* (WSI). The images are captured at one or more optical magnifications and stored in a pyramidal data structure with different resolutions (akin to using different objectives on a conventional light microscope). Most often used are $20 \times$ or $40 \times$ objectives with an appropriate aperture to enable high resolution together with the camera detector chip pixel size, e.g. real optical resolution of 230 nm per pixel [2]. Details from any area of the slide can be accessed through virtual magnification, without affecting the quality of the image, and most systems also allow digital zoom beyond the actual maximum optical resolution for a better screen size of the analyzed structures.

Digitization of slides allows the use of artificial intelligence (AI) for image analysis. During the past years intensive efforts have been taken in this field. AI and image analysis in histology have become a game changer for surgical pathology diagnostics [3–8], drug development [9] and the investigation of disease mechanisms [10,11]. Digital and computational pathology can be used to automate and support tasks routinely performed by pathologists and also to extract complex information and insights not obviously visible to the pathology specialist such as prognosis and outcome prediction and the efficiency of drugs using solely hematoxylin and eosin (H&E) sections [12–14].

Deep Learning (DL) techniques contribute to the analysis of surgical pathology specimens. Specific results can be obtained much faster, e.g. the evaluation of the mitotic rate in cancer specimens, and are often less prone to inter- and intra-observer variations. Such concepts of AI/DL decision support systems (AIDSS) are also economically interesting where the pathologists work in tandem with the computational tools. In recent studies, the joint analysis by pathologists and AIDSS provides better accuracy and reproducibility when compared to analyses performed by unassisted pathologists [3,15–18].

Diagnosis and treatment of cancer are complex tasks, as cancer can appear in numerous locations and is a heterogeneous group of different entities/sub-entities with varying appearances, each with characteristic biology and genetics. To analyze a lesion that is suspected to be cancerous, it is removed or biopsied stereotactically and then submitted to the diagnostic pathology service for general processing: tissue sample registration, fixation, embedding, sectioning, staining, and sequencing. The two types of preparation methods most commonly used are fresh-frozen tissue sections (FS) or formalin-fixed, paraffin-embedded (FFPE) sections. Frozen sections can be prepared rapidly (within minutes) even during surgery and therefore are of most practical value in situations where an immediate answer is required, e.g. to decide how to proceed with the surgery. One drawback of frozen sections is their relatively reduced quality compared to FFPE sections.

Image analysis applications for WSIs include the detection of tumor entities, recognition of invasion patterns, metastatic dissemination, lymph node involvement, and spatial assessment of tumor heterogeneity including inflammatory infiltrates, vascularization patterns, histological grading and other types of scoring. When computational pathology was in its infancy, it was common to hear pathologists say: “Why should we develop a technology that would make us obsolete?” Nowadays, pathologists embrace the added value of using AI solutions that serve as fast and valuable decision-support tools, and a current saying is that pathologists who use AIDSS will eventually replace pathologists who do not. In a recent study that tested a histopathologic classification task of liver cancer, pathologists tended to perform better when they used the output of an AI model, as compared to either the AI model or the physicians alone [16]. Thus, a framework of a joint effort by a pathology expert and AI systems seems to be the promising direction in the future.

While the creation of new AI solutions for research is thriving, there are still barriers that hamper mass adoption of computational pathology in the clinical setting.

Firstly, building a digital pathology infrastructure is expensive and

requires large efforts to start with [1]. To begin with, a decent way to scan slides is required. For research, this can be done with a smartphone, with a camera attached to the microscope, or using a low-capacity scanner. But in order to facilitate high-scale routine operations, slide scanners, image management systems, computing and archiving platforms, and a bundle of AI modules or an AI solutions creation platform are needed, all of which has to be compliant with local regulations for the purposes of diagnostics. Building this infrastructure is a time consuming and expensive process, and although the creation of a digital infrastructure was immensely accelerated during COVID to allow remote work, most pathology labs in the world are still not fully digital. However, pathology labs and departments that became fully digital can be found all over the world. In a recent publication by Schwen et al. [19], the authors provide an overview of lessons learnt from the digitization process of pathology labs. Still, the significant costs involved in transitioning to a fully digital lab makes this process very slow. Ardon et al. [20] published an extensive article on the financial aspects of digital pathology, providing an investment calculator for informed decision making.

Secondly, legal regulatory aspects make AI solutions for diagnostics a long process. Image analysis [21] is a solid field in healthcare, and several solutions for medical image analysis are certified as diagnostic devices. Still, the use of AI technology to create new algorithms introduced a challenge to regulatory bodies [22]. While we can provide the flow and details of a traditional image analysis solution; it is much harder to provide explanations for AI-based decisions. Regulatory bodies require the AI solution not only to be validated, but also to be understandable. This motivates research in explainable AI [23]. Nevertheless, regulatory approval is adapting to AI-based solutions, as can be seen in a recent announcement of the FDA [WEB1] that reveals the authorization of 950 AI/ML-enabled medical devices, where more than 213 of which were approved between August 2023 and June 2024. Of the 950 FDA approved AI solutions [WEB2] only one is in the field of pathology (Paige Prostate by Page.AI, New York City, NY, USA).

Thirdly, the field faces a lack of standardization. Computational pathology needs digitization. So, the first step is scanning the slides. Looking at the main providers of pathology scanners, we see that each provider has their own proprietary file format. This adds to the complexity of accessing, viewing and analyzing data. A number of efforts are underway to establish standardization in the DP field. One notable effort is that of NEMA, the *National Electrical Manufacturers Association*. NEMA is a standards organization based in the United States that develops and publishes standards for various industries, including medical imaging. DICOM® (Digital Imaging and Communications in Medicine) is a standard developed by NEMA to facilitate the exchange of medical images and related information between different imaging devices and information systems in healthcare settings. NEMA developed the DICOM standard for radiology together with equipment manufacturers, and has subsequently introduced DICOM WSI to the field of pathology [24–26]. This effort is yet to see mass adoption by major players in digital and computational pathology, but has led to conversion tools to the format from the proprietary ones [27].

Another leading standardization effort is *Open Microscopy Environment* (OME), a libre and open-source project [WEB3], they provide the OMERO platform and OME-TIFF file format. Additionally, they publish *Bio-Formats*, a software library that enables reading and converting more than 140 proprietary WSI file formats [28].

Standardization is also a complex issue when it comes to AI solutions. As an example, consider the numerous AI solutions recently developed for Gleason scoring of prostate cancer: Ibx [WEB4], HALO Prostate.AI by Indica Labs [WEB5], Aiforia Prostate Cancer Suite [WEB6], Paige [WEB7], and AIRA Matrix [WEB8]. A recent publication by Faryna et al. [29] comparing two AI solutions (Paige and AIRA Matrix) has shown to provide similar accuracy metrics. Still, the question of the variability among the different solutions remains an important open issue. Similar efforts as the one of Faryna et al. [29] are needed to create a common

ground for an objective evaluation of the AI solutions being developed. Perhaps an open and public competition between the systems would reveal pros and cons, as is often done for other software benchmarking.

The 3 described barriers must be addressed throughout in order to increase the number of AI algorithms that can be used in routine pathology workflows, which is the minority at the moment.

There are also, as in any domain that AI enters, ethical concerns [30] regarding potential data privacy breaches [31], systemic algorithmic bias (reviewed in Ref. [32]) and harm related to erroneous AI-generated outputs [33].

2. Intraoperative AI for surgical pathology

Intraoperative pathology consultation is a standard of surgical management in many cases and requires speedy and optimal communication between surgeons and pathologists. Frozen section examination is routinely performed for sentinel lymph node status, surgical margin assessment, and especially in neurosurgery also for entity and malignancy determination [34,35]. Surgeons adapt their surgical plans according to the pathologists' assessment of the examined tissues. This is a challenging setting as decisions have to be made during the surgery, very quickly and usually with a single consultant pathologist. The purpose of intraoperative consultations include examining a previously unknown or incidental finding, which is often limited to a diagnosis of "benign" or "malignant". When operating on a previously confirmed malignancy, the main purpose of the pathologist is to inform the surgeon whether resection margins are free of residual cancer or infiltrations. If resection margins are inadequate, additional tissue can be removed immediately, without the need for a subsequent operation. As stated earlier, the interpretation of frozen sections is more challenging than that of FFPE sections due to the artefacts caused by the process of rapidly freezing tissue and cryostat cutting.

Recently, Gorman et al. [36] reviewed the current research on machine learning models trained or tested on frozen section WSIs. Models trained on frozen sections performed well when tested on other slide preparations, but models trained only on FFPE images performed significantly worse across other modalities. This suggests not only that ML can be applied to frozen section image processing, but also that the use of frozen section images may increase the model's generalizability for the cost of specificity. Ozyoruk et al. [37] suggested a deep-learning model that improves the quality of frozen section WSIs by transforming them into the style of FFPE WSIs. The model consists of a generative adversarial network incorporating an attention mechanism. The process improved the rates of accurate tumor subtyping by pathologists.

Intraoperative AI solutions for pathology analysis are gradually becoming available. Chen et al. [38] published a paper on the analysis of specimen mammography with AI to predict margin status. Intraoperative specimen mammography is a valuable tool in breast cancer surgery, providing immediate assessment of margins for a resected tumor. However, the accuracy of specimen mammography in detecting microscopic margin positivity is low. The authors developed an AI model to predict the pathologic margin status of resected breast tumors using specimen mammography. The models' accuracy compares favorably with published literature on surgeon and radiologist interpretation of specimen mammography. These models could more precisely guide the extent of resection during the surgical procedure, potentially improving cosmesis and reducing reoperations.

Another advanced AI-based solution to assist intraoperative diagnostics is a new laser-based imaging technique that enables much faster tissue diagnosis during tumor surgery using *Stimulated Raman Histology* (SRH), reviewed in Refs. [39,40]. A digital tissue section can be created directly in the operating room and accessed/diagnosed after just a few minutes. This could replace a process that usually takes much more time, 30 min on average, without such new technology and AI functionality. There are about 120 different types of tumors in the central nervous system [41], and the first step in their treatment is

usually surgery with immediate histology acquisition of the tumor characteristics. With the new laser-based SRH imaging technique, neuropathologists can potentially produce reports within minutes [42,43]. The SRH method in a handheld Raman spectroscopic probe with ML-supported analysis has recently been tested intraoperatively [44]. This multicenter brain tumor study is the first multi-user experience using such systems to detect the most common types of brain tumors, label-free, during surgery and in real time.

3. Postoperative AI for surgical pathology

In contrast to frozen sections, permanent sections are prepared from tissues that have been fixed, dehydrated and embedded in paraffin wax as a supporting medium prior to sectioning. Though requiring more time for preparation (generally 12–24 h), permanent sections offer a number of important advantages over frozen tissue sections. Permanent sections are generally thinner (typically 2–4 μm), whereas frozen sections are typically 4.5–8 μm to avoid freezing artefacts. Moreover, permanent sections are stained more uniformly (frequently using automated staining devices), thus providing better and more consistent overall quality and therefore enabling greater certainty of interpretation. Additionally, nowadays many ancillary tests are based on FFPE sections, such as FISH, immunohistochemical labelling, and molecular pathology techniques, including various sequencing approaches.

Tumor **grading** and tumor **staging** play a central role in estimating the patient's prognosis and in determining the oncologic treatment plan.

It is obvious that objective determinations made by the pathologist on resected tumor specimens have a very critical impact on accurate tumor grading and staging. Tumor grading refers to the pathologist's judgment as to a tumor's degree of resemblance to the original healthy tissue (differentiation) and growth rate, often on a scale of 0–3 in surgical pathology [45], and WHO grade 1 through 4 in neuropathology [41], where 0 is for "in-situ" cells that haven't invaded or spread yet (does not apply for brain tumors in neuropathology), and III representing the least differentiated (WHO grade 4 for brain tumors), fastest dividing tumors (i.e. tumors presumed to have the worst prognosis).

Formal grading systems have been improved during the recent years; however, they still have shortcomings. Firstly, a different scale is required for each type of tumor, and scoring is subjective and sometimes difficult to reproduce [46–48]. Secondly, tumors are typically heterogeneous and areas differing significantly in differentiation and mitotic activity exist side by side, with the attendant risk of sampling errors. Because of the prognosis being invariably linked to the highest grade portions of a given tumor, it follows that, for accurate diagnosis and grading, sufficient tissue samples and microscopic sections must be examined so that the most aggressive areas can be found.

Currently, there are huge research efforts for postoperative AI-based analysis of WSI, reviewed in Refs. [49,50]. Recent publications can also be found in the worldwide leading pathology conferences, e.g. USCAP [WEB9], ECP [WEB10], PathVisions [WEB11], and ECDIP [WEB12]. In addition, commercial solutions are becoming available worldwide for diagnostic purposes. Examples include (in alphabetical order, list not exhaustive) Aiforia (Helsinki, Finland) providing assessment suites for different cancer types; Aiosyn (Nijmegen, The Netherlands) offering a solution for mitotic figure counting; Ibex (Tel Aviv, Israel) providing diagnostic solutions for prostate, breast and gastric cancers; MindPeak (Hamburg, Germany) offering diagnostic solutions for Ki67, PD-L1, HER2 and ER/PR quantification of breast and lung cancers; Paige (NYC, New York, USA) offering diagnostic solutions for prostate (the only FDA-approved solution) and breast cancer, and others.

4. Quality assessment of digital slides

Exploiting the full potential of digital and computational pathology, and transferring these tools into clinical practice is challenging [1]. Dealing with artefacts that occur during sample preparation and

digitization may be challenging [19,51]. Quality control of surgical biopsies is imperative to identify and correct potential errors such as a misidentified sample, inappropriate container, insufficient fixation, contamination, tissue adequacy and, for cytology samples, staining quality and determination of cellularity [52].

Once the slides are prepared, they can be digitized using WSI scanners. With different WSI scanners available using different technologies, the digitization of slides can produce very different results [53,54]. Consequently, the parameters of each WSI scanner component can impact the quality of the WSI and therefore its further interpretation. In addition, as pointed out by Ogura et al. [55] the same slide repeatedly scanned with the same WSI scanner will not produce completely identical WSIs. As such, the FDA has designated WSI systems as class III (highest risk) medical devices. When using a WSI, validation must first be performed to ensure that the diagnostic performance based on digitized slides is at least equivalent to that of glass slides and light microscopy. Pantanowitz et al. [56] provided guidelines on this topic. Slide preparation can introduce many artefacts that may impact the readability of the slide. This is also the case with slide digitization (e.g. with blurred areas). Both these kinds of artefacts can be disruptive for either a visual analysis by a pathologist or an automated analysis by an AI tool.

WSI scanners employ different image compression techniques to attain reasonable file sizes [53]. This compression can be lossless or lossy, which results in a much smaller file size, but introduces different compression artefacts [lossless compression by definition means no artefacts, bit-perfect reproduction] [57].

Typically, image compression is measured using the quality factor (QF) or compression rate. An uncompressed image has a QF of 100. If the scanner uses a QF that is too low, compression artefacts will appear, which are mostly visible as block effects. Some studies investigated the optimization of compression standards for WSI scanners [54]. Although there is no consensus regarding acceptability of image compression levels, JPEG is thought to allow a compression rate between 10:1 and 20:1, and between 30:1 and 50:1 for JPEG2000, without the loss of diagnostic information [58].

WSI scanners can provide very different results depending on their optical components and internal color calibration (if any). Consequently, it is inevitable for WSIs to have vast variations in their color appearance among different institutions because of different staining protocols and different scanners [54]. The computational pathology community has embraced this problem and has tried to address it through different means: color calibration, color normalization and stain normalization [54]. An additional important issue is that of WSI parts out of focus.

The field of quality control of WSIs is just in its infancy. The main issues are known and are related to artefact detection, staining quality, and focus [54]. Methods that have been proposed separately for each quality issue have limitations in terms of accuracy and reproducibility on datasets different from the ones used for the training of the algorithms [54,59,60]. Future research will hopefully achieve a quality control tool based on AI that is able to recognize all the quality problems and to decide what to do with the slide from rejection, advising re-staining or rescanning, to considering the slide as analyzable by an AI system.

5. AI and foundation models for pathology

Foundation models are large-scale machine learning models, typically involving deep learning architectures, which serve as a base or foundation for various downstream tasks [61]. These models are pre-trained on vast amounts of diverse data, allowing them to learn a wide array of patterns and knowledge. The pre-training process involves learning of general features from the data, which then can be fine-tuned for specific applications. Foundation models are known for their versatility and ability to generalize across different tasks, making them a cornerstone in the development of AI systems. They enable researchers

and developers to leverage a single, robust model to tackle numerous challenges, significantly reducing the time and resources required to build specialized models from scratch.

The use of foundation models for pathology is evident in two domains: Large Language Models (LLMs) and foundation models for image analysis.

First, we will discuss pathology and LLMs. Diagnostic pathology reports present information comprehensively and includes sufficient details to allow for decision making by clinicians. Pathological reporting can benefit greatly from recent advances in LLMs. Recently, GPT-4 was able to pass all 3 United States Medical Licensing Examination steps and was able to give cogent reasoning as to how it selected the correct answers [62]. In a recent article by Singh [WEB13] it was pointed out that current off-the-shelf LLMs have been trained on more than a billion scale datasets found from the internet. However, these datasets do not include representative amounts of medical data. It is therefore critical to build medical domain specific models that combine text-based and vision-based information. They point out that visual-language foundation models work well for medical images in a research setting. However, with the main limitation being availability of diverse petascale data, it is still a challenge to generate models that can generalize to a real-world setting. Larger datasets for training will be needed, which can be overcome by federated models of data sharing.

Gagan et al. suggest two basic ways that LLMs could be implemented with molecular pathology [63]. The first is that chat bots could be incorporated in software packages to annotate or interpret molecular findings. The second is that LLMs could be trained on molecular inputs such as DNA, RNA, or protein sequences to find functional significance of novel variants. They also point out that both applications have several challenges that must be overcome before clinical implementation. According to Gagan et al., the most significant limitation for clinical use of LLMs has to do with the propensity of LLMs to “hallucinate”, which is defined as producing content that is nonsensical or untruthful [63].

Another important use case of foundation models in pathology is image analysis. Recently, several new foundation models, so-called vision transformers (ViT), were introduced:

The *GigaPath* ViT [64] was pre-trained on 1.3 billion 256×256 pathology image tiles in 171,189 whole slides from Providence [WEB14], a large US health network comprising 28 cancer centers. The WSI slides originated from more than 30,000 patients covering 31 major tissue types.

Currently, the largest foundation models for computational pathology are Virchow [65] and Virchow2/Virchow2G [66], the latter two new models Virchow2, a 632 million parameter ViT, and Virchow2G, a 1.9 billion parameter ViT, were each trained with 3.1 million histopathology whole slide images, with diverse tissues and stains from different originating institutions.

Foundation models enjoy a high popularity in many domains, especially for the creation of contents (e.g. texts and images). The recent examples for pathology see like the tip of the iceberg.

6. Surgical pathology and AI applications - where do we go?

In addition to histopathological diagnosis, **molecular profiling** of cancer has proven indispensable in modern-day cancer pathology and oncotherapy. Molecular profiling improves the diagnoses related to real patient outcomes. It can be expanded with AI to generate predictions for novel molecular biomarkers and to specifically determine effect of targeted therapies [67]. Drug outcome predictions based on AI models are being developed using clinical trials retrospectively.

There is also a thriving effort to create new biomarkers based on the spatial analysis of cells, proteins, lipids, metabolites and RNA from tissue slides.

Spatial biology analyses in pathology involve the integration of spatial morphological, e.g. cell morphology and distribution, and molecular information, e.g. proteomics and transcriptomics, into the

analysis of WSIs [68–70]. Traditionally, pathology analysis has focused on examining tissue samples to understand the presence and characteristics of diseases. Spatial biology adds an extra layer of technical and analytical complexity. The interpretation of these multilayered datasets demand assistance of AI/ML tools, e.g. to assess the spatial context of biological structures within tissues (pattern recognition) including the relationships between different cell types, their distribution, and their interactions with neighboring cells and structures. Extensive multidimensional molecular datasets (including spatial) and other biological data (e.g. patient-related) allow to establish diagnostic, predictive and therapeutic setups. As an example, studying the spatial distribution of immune cells within tumor samples can provide insights into the tumor microenvironment and guide immunotherapy strategies [71]. Similarly, understanding the spatial organization of biomarkers within tissues can help in diagnosing and predicting disease outcomes [72].

The quest for finding significant molecular signatures from the morphological characteristics embedded in the WSIs is an active field of research. For instance, recent research has revealed that statistical models could link histomorphological traits to mutations [13,14,73].

Mutations and epigenomic modifications are known to cause large variation of disease course and treatment. The recovery of molecular features from H&E stained WSIs is an active field of research [74–76]. The capability to predict gene expression using WSIs, either as an intermediate modality or as an outcome, has been demonstrated to aid diagnosis and prognosis [77]. Previous studies have drawn attention to gene expression prediction using WSI; however, the file size of WSIs and the amount of well-annotated data still impose serious challenges. In particular, sample selection and WSI representation is an open topic that is often handled arbitrarily.

In a recent Delphi study, an international panel of experts were asked about the state of pathology in 2030 [78]. There was agreement that AI would improve multiple laboratory key performance indicators, that histopathologic analyses would become more quantitative and diagnostic reports more complex. There was also agreement that AI would lead to greater standardization of diagnostic and pre-analytical processes. It was also agreed that by 2030 there will be growth in computational pathology as a subspecialty, with AI applications assisting pathologists in making more accurate, standardized, objective, quantitative, and complete diagnoses. It was also agreed that pathologists would be routinely involved in new tasks related to AI incorporation into their workflows, participating in the development of AI solutions and contributing to the definition of new patient categories. AI was expected to positively impact many aspects of the pathology workflow, with several applications expected to be in routine use by 2030. For the analysis and interpretation of histologic images, these included algorithms for identifying hotspots (i.e. counting mitotic activity), microorganisms (acid-fast bacilli and *Helicobacter pylori*), neoplasia, and tumor grading. There was also certainty that AI would be in routine use for automated quantification of immunohistochemical (IHC) and immunofluorescent (IF) biomarkers, counting of mitotic figures and lymphocytes, and lymph node metastasis identification. Manual tasks expected to be replaced by AI included size measurement and perineural and lymphovascular invasion detection in malignancies. In addition, they expect that AI-based computational/virtual staining could replace the need for multiplex IHC/IF. The panelists foresaw significant regulatory and ethical challenges posed by AI integration and agreed that both primary diagnostic and secondary, e.g. advisory and assistive, algorithms would have to meet strict regulatory requirements [78]. There was agreement that regulatory bodies would create new guidelines addressing AI integration into pathology, providing specific validation procedures, and simplifying regulatory pathways for AI tools, although clearance of AI software would still be a lengthy and costly process.

Looking beyond 2030, we would like to point out some more intense efforts for the establishment of **optical biopsies** and **mass spectrometry imaging** (MSI) in pathology diagnostics.

The effort towards **optical biopsy** has started decades ago. The term

“optical biopsy” refers to methods that use the properties of light, such as polarization properties and orbital angular momentum, to enable the operator to make an instant diagnosis during a surgical procedure rather than using current histological or cytological analyses based on tissue sectioning and staining. Among the novel imaging techniques suggested are direct stimulated Raman scattering microscopy, *in vivo* microscopy, confocal microscopy, virtual histology, fluorescence imaging, optical coherence tomography, and special molecular imaging techniques [75, 79–88]. A recent example is an optical biopsy system that can distinguish between cancerous and healthy liver tissue. Zherebtsov et al. [89] present a new optical biopsy system that combines diffuse reflectance spectroscopy and lifetime fluorescence measurements to evaluate markers related to cellular metabolism, which differs between healthy and cancerous cells. This could help surgeons to see, in real time, where cancer cells are located so that they can identify the best place to acquire tissue samples, e.g. to determine infiltration margins. This is an exciting direction that promotes glass-free intraoperative pathology analysis.

Mass spectrometry imaging generates large datasets of spatially allocated, quantitative ion mass information by extracting biological molecules with a matrix and ionizing them with a laser (MALDI) or desorption and electrospray ionization (DESI), and measuring time-of-flight (TOF) in an electric field [90,91]. Ion masses can be mapped with molecule and compound libraries to determine the biological molecule content in each of the spatial pixels. MSI can provide proteomic [92], metabolomic and lipidomic information and can generate new dimensions of pathology information beyond current staining procedures, genetics and molecular pathology methods [93], even in the setting of intraoperative diagnostics [94]. The current pathology diagnostics workup includes a panel of molecular genetic or protein expression analysis. Due to the routinely used FFPE pathology workup, the wide field of metabolomics and lipidomics as tissue and disease markers is only marginally used for pathology diagnostics – mostly for inborn metabolic or storage diseases, and much less in the diagnosis of cancer or other diseases. The specific signatures of lipidomic and metabolomic markers in cancer could be assessed in a spatial manner using a combination of innovative technologies, such as MSI and DL [95], and applied as future diagnostic features, or used for future treatment stratification and development. Many cancer entities have specific metabolic and molecular signatures, e.g. glioblastoma (GBM, WHO grade IV¹) which were split into two entities in the most recent WHO classification from 2021 [41]: ‘glioblastoma, WHO grade 4’ (formerly GBM, *IDH* wild-type) and ‘astrocytoma, WHO grade 4, *IDH*-mutated’ (formerly GBM, *IDH*-mutated) due to differences in their biological behavior caused by biologically beneficial *IDH1/2* mutations [41]. Thus, new metabolic and lipidomics markers could expand our knowledge about cancer pathophysiology and enable to define new metabo-subentities for brain tumors and other tumors [90,96–99].

7. Conclusions

AI solutions applied to pathology have already penetrated the medical market and are increasingly used to optimize workflows, while also facilitating surgically oriented requests. With the large amount of digitized data comes the need for structuring and standardization centered on the human expertise.

AI solutions for pathology are being developed immensely. The coming years will be critical in the integration of these solutions into the routine clinical workflow. The success of creating meaningful AI solutions that will be used for clinical practice depends highly on the involvement and contribution of surgeons and pathologists to the development and evaluation of the AI systems. They should be actively involved in finding the right problems to address with AI, the

¹ The former nomenclature used Roman numbers for the different grades I - IV, since 2021 grade 1 - 4.

development of trustworthy solutions and their validation and bringing these AI solution to the pathology workflow. Only a joint effort of the pathology and surgery communities with the AI community will result in a bright future for AI in pathology.

The advances in AI-assisted pathology diagnostics go far beyond simple morphological characterization and can deliver a new mode of diagnostic setting. Here, the professional medical specialist entities of pathology, oncology and genetics merge with originally non-medical specializations, such as molecular biology, bioinformatics, pharmacy, and immunology. This demands a new educational level and the discussion whether it would be helpful to set up a separate professional entity with the full educational and specialization responsibility to for further advancements in the field.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Chen Sagiv: Conceptualization, Investigation, Resources, Writing – original draft. **Ofir Hadar:** Investigation, Resources, Writing – review & editing. **Abderrahman Najjar:** Investigation, Resources, Writing – review & editing. **Jens Pahnke:** Investigation, Resources, Writing – review & editing.

Funding information

J.P. received funding from the DFG (Germany; #263024513), HelseSØ (Norway; #2019055, #2022046), Norges forskningsråd [NFR, Norway; #295910 (NAPI), #327571 (PETABC)] and EIC Pathfinder Open Challenges (EU commission; #101185769).

PETABC is an EU Joint programme - Neurodegenerative Disease Research (JPND) project. PETABC is supported through the following funding organizations under the aegis of JPND – www.jpnd.eu: NFR (Norway; #327571), FFG (Austria; #882717), BMBF (Germany; #01ED2106); MSMT (Czech Republic; #8F21002), LZP (Latvia; #ESRTD/2020/26), ANR (France; #20-JPW2-0002-04), SRC (Sweden; #2020-02905).

NAPI is the Norwegian Advanced Proteomics Infrastructure Network (www.napi.uio.no) supported by Norges forskningsrådet/Norway, #295910).

Competing interests statement

C.S. is CEO of SagivTech Ltd. and DeePathology Ltd.
O.H. is a team leader and research scientist at DeePathology Ltd.
A.N. was a medical advisor for DeePathology Ltd. between Feb 2023–Jun 2023.
J.P. is an academic collaborator of DeePathology Ltd.

References

- [1] Samueli B, et al. Complete digital pathology transition: a large multi-center experience. *Pathol Res Pract* 2024;253:155028. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.prp.2023.155028>.
- [2] Scheffler K, et al. Determination of spatial and temporal distribution of microglia by 230nm-high-resolution, high-throughput automated analysis reveals different amyloid plaque populations in an APP/PS1 mouse model of Alzheimer's disease. *Curr Alzheimer Res* 2011;8:781–8. <https://doi.org/10.2174/156720511797633179>.
- [3] Dy A, et al. AI improves accuracy, agreement and efficiency of pathologists for Ki67 assessments in breast cancer. *Sci Rep* 2024;14:1283. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-024-51723-2>.
- [4] Shmatko A, et al. Artificial intelligence in histopathology: enhancing cancer research and clinical oncology. *Nat Cancer* 2022;3:1026–38. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s43018-022-00436-4>.
- [5] Bahadir CD, et al. Artificial intelligence applications in histopathology. *Nat Rev Electrical Eng* 2024;1:93–108. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s44287-023-00012-7>.
- [6] Kim I, et al. Application of artificial intelligence in pathology: trends and challenges. *Diagnostics* 2022;12. <https://doi.org/10.3390/diagnostics12112794>.
- [7] Shafi S, Parwani AV. Artificial intelligence in diagnostic pathology. *Diagn Pathol* 2023;18:109. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13000-023-01375-z>.

- [8] Abdelsamea MM, et al. A survey on artificial intelligence in histopathology image analysis. *WIREs Data Min Knowledge Discovery* 2022;12. <https://doi.org/10.1002/widm.1474>.
- [9] Mohle L, et al. Dimethyl fumarate does not mitigate cognitive decline and beta-amyloidosis in female APPS1 mice. *Brain Res* 2021;1768:147579. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.brainres.2021.147579>.
- [10] Mohle L, et al. Development of deep learning models for microglia analyses in brain tissue using DeePathology STUDIO. *J Neurosci Methods* 2021;364:109371. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jneumeth.2021.109371>.
- [11] Bascunana P, et al. Machine learning-supported analyses improve quantitative histological assessments of amyloid-beta deposits and activated microglia. *J Alzheimers Dis* 2021;79:597–605. <https://doi.org/10.3233/JAD-201120>.
- [12] McCaffrey C, et al. Artificial intelligence in digital histopathology for predicting patient prognosis and treatment efficacy in breast cancer. *Expert Rev Mol Diagn* 2024;24:363–77. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14737159.2024.2346545>.
- [13] Farahmand S, et al. Deep learning trained on hematoxylin and eosin tumor region of Interest predicts HER2 status and trastuzumab treatment response in HER2+ breast cancer. *Mod Pathol* 2022;35:44–51. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41379-021-00911-w>.
- [14] Erak E, et al. Predicting prostate cancer molecular subtype with deep learning on histopathologic images. *Mod Pathol* 2023;36:100247. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.modpat.2023.100247>.
- [15] Bizzego A, et al. Evaluating reproducibility of AI algorithms in digital pathology with DAPPER. *PLoS Comput Biol* 2019;15:e1006269. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pcbi.1006269>.
- [16] Kiani A, et al. Impact of a deep learning assistant on the histopathologic classification of liver cancer. *NPJ Digit Med* 2020;3:23. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41746-020-0232-8>.
- [17] Al-Thelaya K, et al. Applications of discriminative and deep learning feature extraction methods for whole slide image analysis: a survey. *J Pathol Inf* 2023;14:100335. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpi.2023.100335>.
- [18] McGenity C, et al. Artificial intelligence in digital pathology: a systematic review and meta-analysis of diagnostic test accuracy. *NPJ Digit Med* 2024;7:114. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41746-024-01106-8>.
- [19] Schwen LO, et al. Digitization of pathology labs: a review of lessons learned. *Lab Invest J Techn Methods Pathol* 2023;103:100244. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.labinv.2023.100244>.
- [20] Ardon O, et al. Understanding the financial aspects of digital pathology: a dynamic customizable return on investment calculator for informed decision-making. *J Pathol Inf* 2024;15:100376. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpi.2024.100376>.
- [21] Galic I, et al. Machine learning empowering personalized medicine: a comprehensive review of medical image analysis methods. *Electronics* 2023;12. <https://doi.org/10.3390/electronics12214411>.
- [22] Wischmeyer T, Rademacher T. *Regulating artificial intelligence*. 2020.
- [23] Klauschen F, et al. Toward explainable artificial intelligence for precision pathology. *Annual Rev Pathol* 2024;19:541–70. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-pathmechdis-051222-113147>.
- [24] Herrmann MD, et al. Implementing the DICOM standard for digital pathology. *J Pathol Inf* 2018;9:37. https://doi.org/10.4103/jpi.jpi_42_18.
- [25] Clunie DA. DICOM format and protocol standardization-A core requirement for digital pathology success. *Toxicol Pathol* 2021;49:738–49. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0192623320965893>.
- [26] Clunie DA. Dual-personality DICOM-TIFF for whole slide images: a migration technique for legacy software. *J Pathol Inf* 2019;10:12. https://doi.org/10.4103/jpi.jpi_93_18.
- [27] Gu Q, et al. Dicom_wsi: a Python implementation for converting whole-slide images to digital imaging and communications in medicine compliant files. *J Pathol Inf* 2021;12:21. https://doi.org/10.4103/jpi.jpi_88_20.
- [28] Linkert M, et al. Metadata matters: access to image data in the real world. *J Cell Biol* 2010;189:777–82. <https://doi.org/10.1083/jcb.201004104>.
- [29] Faryna K, et al. Evaluation of artificial intelligence-based Gleason grading algorithms "in the wild". *Mod Pathol* 2024;37:100563. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.modpat.2024.100563>.
- [30] Chauhan C, Gullapalli RR. Ethics of AI in pathology: current paradigms and emerging issues. *Am J Pathol* 2021;191:1673–83. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ajpath.2021.06.011>.
- [31] Murdoch B. Privacy and artificial intelligence: challenges for protecting health information in a new era. *BMC Med Ethics* 2021;22:122. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12910-021-00687-3>.
- [32] P.S. DV. How can we manage biases in artificial intelligence systems – a systematic literature review. *Int J Info Manag Data Insights* 2023;3. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jjime.2023.100165>.
- [33] Dalalah D, Dalalah OMA. The false positives and false negatives of generative AI detection tools in education and academic research: the case of ChatGPT. *Int J Manag Educ* 2023;21:100822. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijme.2023.100822>.
- [34] Elshanbary AA, et al. The diagnostic accuracy of intraoperative frozen section biopsy for diagnosis of sentinel lymph node metastasis in breast cancer patients: a meta-analysis. *Environ Sci Pollut Res Int* 2022;29:47931–41. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-022-20569-4>.
- [35] Garcia MT, et al. Accuracy of frozen section in intraoperative margin assessment for breast-conserving surgery: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *PLoS One* 2021;16:e0248768. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0248768>.
- [36] Gorman BG, et al. Artificial intelligence and frozen section histopathology: a systematic review. *J Cutan Pathol* 2023;50:852–9. <https://doi.org/10.1111/cup.14481>.

- [37] Ozyoruk KB, et al. A deep-learning model for transforming the style of tissue images from cryosectioned to formalin-fixed and paraffin-embedded. *Nat Biomed Eng* 2022;6:1407–19. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41551-022-00952-9>.
- [38] Chen KA, et al. Analysis of specimen mammography with artificial intelligence to predict margin status. *Ann Surg Oncol* 2023;30:7107–15. <https://doi.org/10.1245/s10434-023-14083-1>.
- [39] Ma L, et al. Stain-free histopathology with stimulated Raman scattering microscopy. *Anal Chem* 2024;96:7907–25. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.analchem.4c02061>.
- [40] Hollon TC, et al. Near real-time intraoperative brain tumor diagnosis using stimulated Raman histology and deep neural networks. *Nat Med* 2020;26:52–8. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41591-019-0715-9>.
- [41] Louis DN, et al. The 2021 WHO classification of tumors of the central nervous system: a summary. *Neuro Oncol* 2021;23:1231–51. <https://doi.org/10.1093/neuonc/noab106>.
- [42] Di L, et al. Stimulated Raman histology for rapid intraoperative diagnosis of gliomas. *World neurosurgery* 2021;150:e135–43. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wneu.2021.02.122>.
- [43] Appay R, et al. Live stimulated Raman histology for the near-instant assessment of central nervous system samples. *J Phys Chem B* 2023;127:3624–31. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jpcc.3c01156>.
- [44] Ember K, et al. In situ brain tumor detection using a Raman spectroscopy system-results of a multicenter study. *Sci Rep* 2024;14:13309. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-024-62543-9>.
- [45] Kozakowski N. Grading and staging in pathology. In: Altaieb A, editor. *Surgical pathology*. City: Springer International Publishing; 2021. p. 109–10.
- [46] Bianchi S, et al. Reproducibility of histological diagnoses and diagnostic accuracy of non palpable breast lesions. *Pathol Res Pract* 1994;190:69–76. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0344-0338\(11\)80498-x](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0344-0338(11)80498-x).
- [47] Mazer BL, et al. False-positive pathology: improving reproducibility with the next generation of pathologists. *Lab Invest J Techn Methods Pathol* 2019;99:1260–5. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41374-019-0257-2>.
- [48] Jackson SL, et al. Diagnostic reproducibility: what happens when the same pathologist interprets the same breast biopsy specimen at two points in time? *Ann Surg Oncol* 2017;24:1234–41. <https://doi.org/10.1245/s10434-016-5695-0>.
- [49] Petříková D, Cimrák I. Survey of recent deep neural networks with strong annotated supervision in histopathology. *Computation* 2023;11. <https://doi.org/10.3390/computation11040081>.
- [50] Mall PK, et al. A comprehensive review of deep neural networks for medical image processing: recent developments and future opportunities. *Healthcare Analytics* 2023;4. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.health.2023.100216>.
- [51] Yang Y, et al. Preparing data for artificial intelligence in pathology with clinical-grade performance. *Diagnostics* 2023;13. <https://doi.org/10.3390/diagnostics13193115>.
- [52] Spiridon IA, Seeliger B. Towards optimisation in surgical pathology - the potential of Artificial Intelligence. *BJS Society Ltd* 2023. <https://doi.org/10.58974/bjss/azbc011>.
- [53] Duenweg SR, et al. Whole slide imaging (WSI) scanner differences influence optical and computed properties of digitized prostate cancer histology. *J Pathol Inf* 2023;14:100321. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpi.2023.100321>.
- [54] Brixel R, et al. Whole slide image quality in digital pathology: review and perspectives. *IEEE Access* 2022;10:131005–35. <https://doi.org/10.1109/access.2022.3227437>.
- [55] Ogura M, et al. Impact of blurs on machine-learning aided digital pathology image analysis. *WArtificial Intel Cancer* 2020;1:31–8. <https://doi.org/10.35713/aic.v1.i1.31>.
- [56] Park S, et al. Digital imaging in pathology. *Clin Lab Med* 2012;32:557–84. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cll.2012.07.006>.
- [57] Krupinski EA, et al. Compressing pathology whole-slide images using a human and model observer evaluation. *J Pathol Inf* 2012;3:17. <https://doi.org/10.4103/2153-3539.95129>.
- [58] Kalinski T, et al. Lossless compression of JPEG2000 whole slide images is not required for diagnostic virtual microscopy. *Am J Clin Pathol* 2011;136:889–95. <https://doi.org/10.1309/AJCPYH1Z3TGGAIEP>.
- [59] Patil A, et al. Efficient quality control of whole slide pathology images with human-in-the-loop training. *J Pathol Inf* 2023;14:100306. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpi.2023.100306>.
- [60] Evans H, Snead D. Understanding the errors made by artificial intelligence algorithms in histopathology in terms of patient impact. *NPJ Digit Med* 2024;7:89. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41746-024-01093-w>.
- [61] Moor M, et al. Foundation models for generalist medical artificial intelligence. *Nature* 2023;616:259–65. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-023-05881-4>.
- [62] Brin D, et al. Comparing ChatGPT and GPT-4 performance in USMLE soft skill assessments. *Sci Rep* 2023;13:16492. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-023-43436-9>.
- [63] Gagan J. The potential utility of Large Language Models in molecular pathology. *J Appl Lab Med* 2024;9:159–61. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jalm/jfad102>.
- [64] Xu H, et al. A whole-slide foundation model for digital pathology from real-world data. *Nature* 2024;630:181–8. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-024-07441-w>.
- [65] Vorontsov E, et al. A foundation model for clinical-grade computational pathology and rare cancers detection. *Nat Med* 2024. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41591-024-03141-0>.
- [66] Zimmermann E, et al. Virchow2: scaling self-supervised mixed magnification models in pathology. *arXiv* 2024. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2408.00738>.
- [67] Malone ER, et al. Molecular profiling for precision cancer therapies. *Genome Med* 2020;12:8. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13073-019-0703-1>.
- [68] Levy-Jurgenson A, et al. Spatial transcriptomics inferred from pathology whole-slide images links tumor heterogeneity to survival in breast and lung cancer. *Sci Rep* 2020;10:18802. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-020-75708-z>.
- [69] Schmauch B, et al. A deep learning model to predict RNA-Seq expression of tumours from whole slide images. *Nat Commun* 2020;11:3877. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-020-17678-4>.
- [70] Park YM, Lin DC. Moving closer towards a comprehensive view of tumor biology and microarchitecture using spatial transcriptomics. *Nat Commun* 2023;14:7017. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-023-42960-6>.
- [71] Wang PC, et al. The spatial distribution of immune cell subpopulations in hepatocellular carcinoma. *Cancer Sci* 2022;113:423–31. <https://doi.org/10.1111/cas.15202>.
- [72] Mulholland EJ, Leedham SJ. Redefining clinical practice through spatial profiling: a revolution in tissue analysis. *Ann R Coll Surg Engl* 2024;106:305–12. <https://doi.org/10.1308/rcsann.2023.0091>.
- [73] Chen M, et al. Classification and mutation prediction based on histopathology H&E images in liver cancer using deep learning. *npj Precis Oncol* 2020;4:14. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41698-020-0120-3>.
- [74] Ciga O, et al. Self supervised contrastive learning for digital histopathology. *Machine Lear Appl* 2022;7. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mlwa.2021.100198>.
- [75] de Haan K, et al. Deep learning-based transformation of H&E stained tissues into special stains. *Nat Commun* 2021;12:4884. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-021-25221-2>.
- [76] Couture HD. Deep learning-based prediction of molecular tumor biomarkers from H&E: a practical review. *J Personalized Med* 2022;12. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jpm12122022>.
- [77] Alsaafin A, et al. Learning to predict RNA sequence expressions from whole slide images with applications for search and classification. *Commun Biol* 2023;6:304. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s42003-023-04583-x>.
- [78] Berbis MA, et al. Computational pathology in 2030: a Delphi study forecasting the role of AI in pathology within the next decade. *EBioMedicine* 2023;88:104427. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ebiom.2022.104427>.
- [79] Borovkova M, et al. Screening of alzheimer's disease with multiwavelength Stokes polarimetry in a mouse model. *IEEE Trans Med Imag* 2022;41:977–82. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TMI.2021.3129700>.
- [80] Borovkova M, et al. Assessment of the Alzheimer progression with multiwavelength Stokes polarimetry. 2021. SPIE.
- [81] Borovkova M, et al. Evaluating beta-amyloidosis progression in Alzheimer's disease with Mueller polarimetry. *Biomed Opt Express* 2020;11:4509–19. <https://doi.org/10.1364/BOE.396294>.
- [82] Asaf MZ, et al. Dual contrastive learning based image-to-image translation of unstained skin tissue into virtually stained H&E images. *Sci Rep* 2024;14:2335. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-024-52833-7>.
- [83] Li J, et al. Biopsy-free in vivo virtual histology of skin using deep learning. *Light Sci Appl* 2021;10:233. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41377-021-00674-8>.
- [84] Boktor M, et al. Multi-channel feature extraction for virtual histological staining of photon absorption remote sensing images. *Sci Rep* 2024;14:2009. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-024-52588-1>.
- [85] Bai B, et al. Deep learning-enabled virtual histological staining of biological samples. *Light Sci Appl* 2023;12:57. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41377-023-01104-7>.
- [86] Fujimoto JG, et al. Optical coherence tomography: an emerging technology for biomedical imaging and optical biopsy. *Neoplasia* 2000;2:9–25. <https://doi.org/10.1038/sj.neo.7900071>.
- [87] Manifold B, Fu D. Quantitative stimulated Raman scattering microscopy: promises and pitfalls. *Annu Rev Anal Chem* 2022;15:269–89. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-anchem-061020-015110>.
- [88] Shi L, et al. Advances in stimulated Raman scattering imaging for tissues and animals. *Quant Imag Med Surg* 2021;11:1078–101. <https://doi.org/10.21037/qims-20-712>.
- [89] Zherebtsov EA, et al. Fluorescence lifetime needle optical biopsy discriminates hepatocellular carcinoma. *Biomed Opt Express* 2022;13:633–46. <https://doi.org/10.1364/BOE.447687>.
- [90] Chung HH, et al. Next-generation pathology practices with mass spectrometry imaging. *Mass Spectrom Rev* 2023;42:2446–65. <https://doi.org/10.1002/mas.21795>.
- [91] Eberlin LS. DESI-MS imaging of lipids and metabolites from biological samples. *Methods in molecular biology* (Clifton, NJ) 2014;1198:299–311. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4939-1258-2_20.
- [92] Norris JL, Caprioli RM. Imaging mass spectrometry: a new tool for pathology in a molecular age. *Proteomics Clin Appl* 2013;7:733–8. <https://doi.org/10.1002/prca.201300055>.
- [93] Goncalves JPL, et al. Mass spectrometry imaging spatial tissue analysis toward personalized medicine. *Life* 2022;12. <https://doi.org/10.3390/life12071037>.
- [94] Basu SS, et al. Rapid MALDI mass spectrometry imaging for surgical pathology. *npj Precis Oncol* 2019;3:17. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41698-019-0089-y>.
- [95] Paul B, et al. An integrated mass spectrometry imaging and digital pathology workflow for objective detection of colorectal tumours by unique atomic signatures. *Chem Sci* 2021;12:10321–33. <https://doi.org/10.1039/d1sc02237g>.
- [96] Fack F, et al. Altered metabolic landscape in IDH-mutant gliomas affects phospholipid, energy, and oxidative stress pathways. *EMBO Mol Med* 2017;9:1681–95. <https://doi.org/10.15252/emmm.201707729>.

- [97] Garrett M, et al. Metabolic characterization of isocitrate dehydrogenase (IDH) mutant and IDH wildtype gliomaspheres uncovers cell type-specific vulnerabilities. *Cancer Metabol* 2018;6:4. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40170-018-0177-4>.
- [98] Jalbert LE, et al. Metabolic profiling of IDH mutation and malignant progression in infiltrating glioma. *Sci Rep* 2017;7:44792. <https://doi.org/10.1038/srep44792>.
- [99] Priyadarshani P, et al. Investigation of MSC potency metrics via integration of imaging modalities with lipidomic characterization. *Cell Rep* 2024;43:114579. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.celrep.2024.114579>.

Web references

- [100] WEB1]. <https://www.fda.gov/medical-devices/software-medical-device-samd/artificial-intelligence-and-machine-learning-aiml-enabled-medical-devices>. [Accessed 31 August 2024].
- [101] WEB2]. <https://www.fda.gov/medical-devices/software-medical-device-samd/artificial-intelligence-and-machine-learning-aiml-enabled-medical-devices>. [Accessed 31 August 2024].
- [102] WEB3]. <https://www.openmicroscopy.org/>. [Accessed 31 August 2024].
- [103] WEB4]. <https://ibex-ai.com/galen-prostate/>. [Accessed 31 August 2024].
- [104] WEB5]. <https://indicalab.com/news/halo-prostate-ai-a-tool-for-automated-detection-and-gleason-grading-of-prostate-cancer/>. [Accessed 31 August 2024].
- [105] WEB6]. <https://www.aiforia.com/aiforia-clinical-solutions>. [Accessed 31 August 2024].
- [106] WEB7. <https://info.paige.ai/prostate>. [Accessed 31 August 2024].
- [107] WEB8]. <https://www.airamatrix.com>. [Accessed 31 August 2024].
- [108] WEB9]. <https://uscap.org/uscap-annual-meeting/>. [Accessed 31 August 2024].
- [109] WEB10. <https://www.esp-congress.org/>. [Accessed 31 August 2024].
- [110] WEB11]. <https://digitalpathologyassociation.org/pathology-visions-conference/>. [Accessed 31 August 2024].
- [111] WEB12]. <https://digitalpathologysociety.org>. [Accessed 31 August 2024].
- [112] WEB13. <https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/pathologists-perspective-applications-artificial-ai-large-singh-md/>. [Accessed 31 August 2024].
- [113] WEB14. <https://www.providence.org>. [Accessed 31 August 2024].